

Line Cut Vertex Digraphs of Digraphs

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Abstract: In this paper we define the digraph valued function (digraph operator) namely, the line cut vertex digraph $L_c(D)$ of a digraph D . The problem of reconstructing a digraph from its line cut vertex digraph is presented. Also, outer planarity and maximal outer planarity properties of these digraphs are discussed.

Key Words: Line digraph, cut vertex, complete bipartite subdigraph, line cut vertex digraph, Smarandachely line cut vertex digraph.

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§1. Introduction

Notations and definitions not introduced here can be found in [2,3]. For a simple graph G with vertex set $V(G) = \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n\}$ and cut vertex set $C(G) = \{C_1, C_2, \dots, C_r\}$, detailed by V.R.Kulli et al.[4] gave the following definition. The *line cut vertex graph* of G , written $n(G)$, is the graph whose vertices are the edges $E(G)$ and cut vertices $C(G)$ of G , with two vertices of $n(G)$ adjacent whenever the corresponding edges of G are adjacent or the corresponding members of G are incident, and where the edges and cut vertices of G are called its *members*. Generally, a *Smarandachely line cut vertex digraph* $n_S(G)$ for $S \subset E(G) \cup C(G)$ is such a graph with vertices $E(G) \cup C(G)$ and members are adjacent if and only if they are adjacent or incident in $\langle S \rangle_G$. Clearly, if $S = E(G) \cup C(G)$, then the Smarandachely line cut vertex digraph $n_S(G)$ of G is nothing else but $n(G)$.

Recently, there has been an extension of this topic to trees [5]. In this paper, we extend the definition of the line cut vertex graph of a graph to a directed graph. M.Aigner [1] defines the *line digraph* of a digraph as follows. Let D be a digraph with n vertices v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n and m arcs and $L(D)$ its associated *line digraph* with n' vertices and m' arcs. We immediately have $n' = m$ and $m' = \sum_{i=1}^n d^-(v_i) \cdot d^+(v_i)$. Furthermore, the in-degree, respectively out-degree of a vertex $v' = (v_i, v_j)$ in $L(D)$ are $d^-(v') = d^-(v_i)$ and $d^+(v') = d^+(v_j)$. Also, a digraph D is

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said to be a *line digraph* if it is isomorphic to the line digraph of a certain digraph H [6].

We need some concepts and notations on directed graphs. A *directed graph* (or just *digraph*) D consists of a finite non-empty set $V(D)$ of elements called *vertices* and a finite set $A(D)$ of ordered pair of distinct vertices called *arcs*. Here $V(D)$ is the *vertex set* and $A(D)$ is the *arc set* of D . For an arc (u, v) or uv of D , the first vertex u is its *tail*, and the second vertex v is its *head*. A digraph without any arcs is called *totally disconnected*. An out-star (an in-star) in D is a star in the underlying undirected graph of D such that all arcs are directed out of (into) the center. The out-star and in-star of order k is denoted by S_k^+ and S_k^- , respectively. The *out-degree* of a vertex v , written $d^+(v)$, is the number of arcs going out from v and the *in-degree* of a vertex v , written $d^-(v)$, is the number of arcs coming into v . The *total degree* of a vertex v , written $td(v)$, is the number of arcs incident with v . We immediately have $td(v) = d^-(v) + d^+(v)$. A vertex v for which $d^+(v) = d^-(v) = 0$ is called an *isolate*. A vertex v is called a *transmitter* or a *receiver* according as $d^+(v) > 0, d^-(v) = 0$ or $d^+(v) = 0, d^-(v) > 0$.

A *cut set* of D is defined as a minimal set of vertices whose removal increases the number of connected components of D . A cut set of size one is called a *cut vertex*. A *tournament* is a nontrivial complete asymmetric digraph. A tournament of order n is denoted by T_n . A *semi-star digraph*, denoted by $D_{1,n}, n \geq 2$, is a directed graph with $(n + 1)$ vertices and n arcs; n vertices have total degree exactly one, and one has n .

Since most of the results and definitions for undirected planar graphs are valid for planar digraphs also, the following definitions hold good for planar digraphs. A *planar drawing* of a digraph D is a drawing of D in which no two distinct arcs intersect. A digraph is said to be *planar* if it admits a planar drawing. If D is a planar digraph, then the *inner vertex number* $i(D)$ of D is the minimum number of vertices not belonging to the boundary of the exterior region in any embedding of D in the plane. A digraph D is *outerplanar* if $i(D) = 0$. An outerplanar digraph is said to be *maximal outerplanar* if no arc can be added to it without losing its outer planarity.

§2. Line Cut Vertex Digraph of a Digraph

For a connected digraph D , the *line cut vertex digraph* $Q = L_c(D)$ has vertex set $V(Q) = A(D) \cup C(D)$, where $C(D)$ is the cut vertex set of D . The arc set

$$A(Q) = \begin{cases} ab : a, b \in A(D), \text{ the head of } a \text{ coincides with the tail of } b, \\ Cd : C \in C(D), d \in A(D), \text{ the tail of } d \text{ is } C, \\ dC : C \in C(D), d \in A(D), \text{ the head of } d \text{ is } C. \end{cases}$$

§3. Decomposition and Reconstruction

A digraph is a *complete bipartite digraph* if its vertex set can be partitioned into two sets A, B in such a way that every arc has its initial vertex in A and its terminal vertex in B and any two vertices $a \in A$ and $b \in B$ are joined by an arc. An arc (u, v) of D is said to be an *end arc*

if u is the transmitter and v is the receiver.

Let D be a digraph with vertex set $V(D) = \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n\}$ and cut vertex set $C(D) = \{C_1, C_2, \dots, C_r\}$. We consider the following three cases.

Case 1. Let v be a vertex of D with $d^-(v) = \alpha$ and $d^+(v) = \beta$. Then α arcs coming into v and the β arcs going out of v give rise to a complete bipartite subdigraph with α tails and β heads and $\alpha \cdot \beta$ arcs joining each tail with each head. This is the decomposition of $L(D)$ into mutually arc disjoint complete bipartite subdigraphs.

Case 2. Let C_j be a cut vertex of D with $d^-(C_j) = \alpha'$. Then α' arcs coming into C_j give rise to a complete bipartite subdigraph with α' tails and a single head (i.e., C_j) and α' arcs joining each tail with C_j .

Case 3. Let C_j be a cut vertex of D with $d^+(C_j) = \beta'$. Then β' arcs going out from C_j give rise to a complete bipartite subdigraph with a single tail (i.e., C_j) and β' heads and β' arcs joining C_j with each head.

Hence by all the above cases, $Q = L_c(D)$ is decomposed into mutually arc-disjoint complete bipartite subdigraphs with $V(Q) = A(D) \cup C(D)$ and arc sets (i) $\cup_{i=1}^n X_i \times Y_i$, where X_i and Y_i are the sets of in-coming and out-going arcs at v_i of D , respectively; (ii) $\cup_{j=1}^r \cup_{k=1}^r Z'_j \times C_k$ such that $Z'_j \times C_k = \phi$ for $j \neq k$; (iii) $\cup_{k=1}^r \cup_{j=1}^r C_k \times Z_j$ such that $C_k \times Z_j = \phi$ for $k \neq j$, where Z'_j and Z_j are the sets of in-coming and out-going arcs at C_j of D , respectively.

Conversely, let H' be a digraph of the type described above. Let us denote each of the complete bipartite subdigraphs obtained by Case 1 by T_1, T_2, \dots, T_l . The vertex set of H is $V(H) = \{t_0, t_1, \dots, t_l, t_{l+1}\}$. The arcs of H are obtained by the following procedure (see [3]).

For each vertex $v \in L(D)$, we draw an arc a_v to H as follows.

Step 1: If $d_{L(D)}^+(v) > 0$, and $d_{L(D)}^-(v) = 0$, then $a_v = (t_0, t_i)$ is an arc, where i is the base(or index) of T_i such that $v \in X_i$;

Step 2: If $d_{L(D)}^+(v) = 0$, and $d_{L(D)}^-(v) > 0$, then $a_v = (t_j, t_{l+1})$ is an arc, where j is the base of T_j such that $v \in Y_j$;

Step 3: If $d_{L(D)}^+(v) > 0$, and $d_{L(D)}^-(v) > 0$, then $a_v = (t_i, t_j)$ is an arc, where i and j are the indices of T_i and T_j such that $v \in X_j \cap Y_i$. Finally, if $L(D)$ has an isolated vertex, then $a_v = (t_0, t_{l+1})$. Note that this method always constructs H with only one vertex of in-degree zero and one vertex of out-degree zero.

We now mark the cut vertices of H as follows. From Case 2 and Case 3, we observe that for every cut vertex C , there exists at most two complete bipartite subdigraphs, one containing C as the tail, and other as head. Let it be C'_j and C''_j , $1 \leq j \leq r$ such that C'_j contains C as the head and C''_j contains C as the tail. Now, if the tails of C'_j and the heads of C''_j are the heads and tails of a single T_i , $1 \leq i \leq l$, then the vertex t_i is a cut vertex in H , where i is the index of T_i . Furthermore, a vertex of an end arc in H whose total degree at least two is a cut vertex. The digraph H thus constructed apparently has H' as line cut vertex digraph. Therefore we have,

Theorem 3.1 *A digraph Q is the line cut vertex digraph of a certain digraph D if and only if $V(Q) = A(D) \cup C(D)$ such that the arc set $A(Q)$ equals: (i) $\cup_{i=1}^n X_i \times Y_i$, where X_i and Y_i are*

the sets of in-coming and out-going arcs at v_i of D , respectively, (ii) $\cup_{j=1}^r \cup_{k=1}^r Z'_j \times C_k$ such that $Z'_j \times C_k = \phi$ for $j \neq k$, (iii) $\cup_{k=1}^r \cup_{j=1}^r C_k \times Z_j$ such that $C_k \times Z_j = \phi$ for $k \neq j$, where Z'_j and Z_j are the sets of in-coming and out-going arcs at C_j of D , respectively.

Proposition 3.2 Let D be a digraph with vertex set $V(D) = \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n\}$ and cut vertex set $C(D) = \{C_1, C_2, \dots, C_r\}$. Then the order and size of $L_c(D)$ are

$$m + \sum_{j=1}^r C_j \quad \text{and} \quad \sum_{i=1}^n d^-(v_i) \cdot d^+(v_i) + \sum_{j=1}^r \{d^-(C_j) + d^+(C_j)\},$$

respectively, where m is the size of D .

Proof Let D be a digraph with $V(D) = \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n\}$ and $C(D) = \{C_1, C_2, \dots, C_r\}$. Then the order of $L_c(D)$ equals the sum of size and cut vertices of D . Thus, $V(L_c(D)) = m + \sum_{j=1}^r C_j$. Now, the size of $L_c(D)$ equals the sum of size of $L(D)$ and the total degree of cut vertices of D . Hence

$$A(L_c(D)) = \sum_{i=1}^n d^-(v_i) \cdot d^+(v_i) + \sum_{j=1}^r \{d^-(C_j) + d^+(C_j)\}. \quad \square$$

Proposition 3.3 Let D be a digraph with vertex set $V(D) = \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n\}$. Then $L(D) \simeq L_c(D)$ if and only if D is a block.

Proof Let D be a digraph with vertex set $V(D) = \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n\}$. Suppose that D is a block. Clearly, D does not have any cut vertex. Thus, the order of $L_c(D)$ is exactly m , where m is the size of D . But, $V(L(D)) = m$. Hence $L(D) \simeq L_c(D)$.

Conversely, suppose that $L(D) \simeq L_c(D)$. Assume that D is not a block. Then there exists at least one cut vertex in D . The order of $L_c(D)$ equals the sum of size and cut vertices of D . But, $V(L(D)) = m$. Thus, the order of $L(D)$ is less than the order of $L_c(D)$. Clearly, $L(D) \not\simeq L_c(D)$, a contradiction. This completes the proof. \square

Theorem 3.4 The line cut vertex digraph $L_c(D)$ of a digraph D is outerplanar if,

- (a) D is a directed path \vec{P}_n on $n \geq 3$ vertices;
- (b) D is an in-star(or an out-star) of order $k, k \geq 3$;
- (c) D is the semi-star digraph $D_{1,3}$.

Proof We consider the cases following:

Case 1. Suppose that D is a directed path \vec{P}_n on $n \geq 3$ vertices. Then $L_c(D)$ is a connected digraph in which every block is T_3 . Clearly, $L_c(D)$ is outerplanar.

Case 2. Suppose that D is an in-star(or an out-star) of order $k, k \geq 3$. Then $L(D)$ is totally disconnected of order $(k - 1)$. The number of cut vertex of D is exactly one. Then $L_c(D)$ is an in-star(or an out-star) of order k . Thus, $L_c(D)$ is outerplanar.

Case 3. Suppose that D is the semi-star digraph $D_{1,3}$. Clearly, D contains exactly one cut

vertex C . By definition, $L(D)$ is either $D_{1,2}$ or totally disconnected of order three. We consider the following two subcases of Case 3.

Subcase 1 If $L(D)$ is $D_{1,2}$, then $L_c(D)$ is $T_4 - e$, which is outerplanar.

Subcase 2 If $L(D)$ is totally disconnected, then $L_c(D)$ is $D_{1,3}$, which is also outerplanar. This completes the proof. \square

Theorem 3.5 *The line cut vertex digraph $L_c(D)$ of a digraph D is maximal outerplanar if and only if D is the directed path \vec{P}_3 .*

Proof We prove this by the method of contradiction. Suppose $L_c(D)$ is maximal outerplanar. Assume that D is the directed path \vec{P}_4 . By Proposition 3.2, the order and size of $L_c(D)$ are $n = 5$ and $m = 6$, respectively. But, $m = 6 < 7 = 2n - 3$. Since every maximal outerplanar digraph with n vertices contains $2n - 3$ arcs, $L_c(D)$ is not maximal outerplanar, a contradiction.

Conversely, suppose that D is \vec{P}_3 . Then $L_c(D)$ is T_3 , which is maximal outerplanar. This completes the proof. \square

§4. Open Problems

We present the following open problems:

- (1) Characterize the digraphs whose line cut vertex digraphs are planar, minimally non-outerplanar, and have crossing number one.
- (2) One can naturally extend this concept to directed trees. ([See [5]).

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